

Reconstructing and Analysing a forgotten World: A 3D-Positioning and Annotation System for the Paintings of the Kucha Project

Radisch, Erik

radisch@saw-leipzig.de

Sächsische Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Leipzig,
Deutschland

ORCID: 0000-0002-0089-9082

The Buddhist cave complexes of Kucha in Xinjiang preserve mural programs from the 5th to 10th centuries. Early 20th-century expeditions photographed and collected large parts of this material, resulting in the removal and worldwide dispersal of many fragments (see Yaldiz 1987; Popova 2008; Dreyer 2015; Zhao 2021). This dispersal obscures their original placement within the caves.

One of the primary objectives of the project “Buddhist murals of Kucha on the Northern Silk Road”¹ is to develop a database-supported information system to document both in-situ paintings and dispersed fragments. Using historical photographs and reports, the project aims to reconstruct the original context of these artworks, thereby re-establishing their positions within the mural composition.

We use the Annotorious annotation tool together with a taxonomy of around 1,200 entries; the system currently contains nearly 11,000 annotated elements.² (Figure 1). Annotations are available online.³

Annotating with Annotorious.

To meaningfully reposition the fragments within their respective caves, it is essential to understand not only what is depicted but also where they were originally located. This

requires a spatial framework reflecting the visual organization of the cave walls.

Most paintings follow square or rhombic register systems (Figure 2), structured in registers (y-axis) and numbers (x-axis). Numbering starts at the entrance and moves inward, top to bottom. Previously, these systems were recorded as text fields—useful for experts, but inaccessible to broader audiences.

Example of the register systems: above in rhombic form, below in square form.

We therefore developed an interactive visualization of register systems that allows users to design layouts, mark positions, and assign content. It distinguishes empty areas (white), lost but known areas (red), and assigned paintings (blue), including uncertain ones (light blue), using semi-transparent SVGs (Figures 3 and 4).

Sample of the new interactive register system in rhombus mode.

Sample of the interactive system in square mode.

To enhance spatial understanding, we projected the register systems onto schematic 3D cave models. Each wall is labeled with its wall-ID to ensure seamless integration. Because many walls are irregular, their silhouettes are included to indicate non-paintable areas (shown in black). As a result, only parts of the register in Figure 5 would be visible in the 3D model. This supports users in positioning register systems accurately.

Projection of the 3D cave shape onto the canvas.

In the final step, SVG elements are overlaid onto the textured cave walls. Although they lose interactivity, mouse positions in 3D space are mapped to canvas coordinates using UV mapping, enabling actions such as informative popups (Figure 6).

To support orientation, preview images (based on annotations that encompass the full artwork) are projected into their corresponding register positions. Due to the schematic model - particularly of the non-rectangular register shapes - these images are slightly reduced in size.

New interactive 3D view of the grid system.

A hierarchical tree of iconographic categories is integrated into the 3D view. Selecting a category highlights all associated paintings in green, supporting spatial exploration of the pictorial program (Figure 7). The tree is derived from the annotation taxonomy and connects visual elements with structured knowledge.

Interaction between content tree and 3D model. Paintings with the requested content are marked green.

The system enables both visual contextualization and content-based spatial analysis of mural programs. As a next step, polygon annotations will be fully integrated into the 3D view, so that only the relevant segments are highlighted when selected (figure 8). This will support targeted motif analysis across cave surfaces. Integration is planned for DHd2026.

Next Step: Integration of polygon annotations into the 3D model. Instead of the entire painting, only relevant regions will be highlighted in the 3D model.

The scholarly value of this approach becomes evident in the analysis of complex mural programs such as those in Kucha, where hundreds of individual scenes, figures, and motifs must be understood in relation to one another and within their spatial setting. Navigating these dense pictorial systems is challenging, even for specialists. By providing a structured spatial framework and an interactive visualization, the system supports researchers in identifying relationships, tracing compositional logic, and comparing iconographic distributions across walls and registers. Because the visualization operates within schematic cave models, multiple caves can be superimposed for comparative analysis, making similarities and differences across sites immediately perceptible and enabling new forms of cross-cave investigation.

Polygon-based annotations are established in 2D image analysis but remain rare in interactive 3D Digital Humanities tools, which often rely on point-based highlighting.⁴ Our approach addresses this gap by enabling surface-specific annotation in 3D space, offering a new method for analyzing complex mural programs. This may also benefit other Digital Humanities projects.⁵ Highlighting regions instead of full images allows richer insight into content relationships.

However, broader adoption of this method remains technically demanding. A more scalable future solution could

involve storing annotations directly as 3D meshes, making them fully interactive within the model. This opens new possibilities for surface-based annotation in cultural heritage.

Footnotes

1. The Project has its own series «Leipzig Kucha Studies». The first Book is: Konczak-Nagel/Zin 2020.
2. <https://annotorious.dev/>
3. <https://kucha.saw-leipzig.de/>
4. A good example might be Kompakkt, which only sets points for annotations: Eide et al. 2019.
5. A good example of another project would be Florence as it was. The paintings, which are presented here in their original spatial context, would benefit greatly, if polygon annotations could also access their pictorial content in detail. Bent et al. 2022

Bibliography

- Bent, G. R. Pfaff, D., Brooks, M, Radpour, R. and Delaney, J.** (2022) A practical workflow for the 3D reconstruction of complex historic sites and their decorative interiors: *Florence As It Was* and the church of Orsanmichele. *Herit Sci* 10, 118 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40494-022-00750-1>
- Dreyer, C.** (2015). *Abenteuer Seidenstraße: Die Berliner Turfan-Expeditionen 1902–1914*. Leipzig: Seemann.
- Eide, Ø., Schubert, Z., Türkoğlu, E., Wieners, J. G., & Niebes, K.** (2019). The intangibility of tangible objects: re-telling artefact stories through spatial multimedia annotations and 3D objects. ICOM Kyoto 2019, 25th ICOM General Conference: Museums as Cultural Hubs: The Future of Tradition, Kyoto. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3878966>
- Konczak-Nagel, I., Zin, M.** (2020). *Essays and Studies in the Art of Kucha*, New Dehli: Dev Publishers & Distributors.
- Popova, I. F.** (ed.) (2008). *Russian Expeditions to Central Asia at the Turn of the 20th Century: Collected Articles*. St Petersburg: Slavia Publishers.
- Yaldiz, M.** (1987). *Archäologie und Kunstgeschichte Chinesisch-Zentralasiens (Xinjiang)*. Leiden: Brill, Handbuch der Orientalistik, Abteilung 7, Kunst und Archäologie, Band 3, Innerasien.
- Zhao, L. 赵莉** (2021). *Kezi'er shiku bihua fuyuan yanjiu 克孜尔石窟壁画复原研究 / A Study on the Restoration of the Kizil Grotto Murals*. Shanghai: Shanghai shuhua chubanshe.